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Exploring Zoom Technology in the Arabic Language Teaching Pronunciation Skills: Basis For Instructional Support Materials

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MAED-EM (Master of Arts in Education Major in Educational Management)

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***A Thesis Presented to the Faculty of the Graduate Studies College of Education, Arts,
and Sciences National University Manila***

***In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the degree Master of Arts in Education
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ABSTRACT

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Pronunciation is one of the most essential language-learning skills since it makes communication possible. Arabic language learners grow increasingly around the globe, but not all can easily access to practice speaking the language, especially the pronunciation. Thus, technology is one of the tools for learning a foreign language. Hence, Zoom technology enhances the learning experience of the students. In this study, the researcher aims to see the effect of Zoom technology on Arabic language learners' pronunciation. A quasi-experimental research design with pre-test, post-test, and interview was used in this study. A total of 50 adult Beginner students were selected and categorized into two groups: Non-Zoom technology (controlled) and Zoom technology (experimental). Paired T-test was utilized to scrutinize the numerical data, while Thematic Content Analysis was adapted to analyze the verbal feedback of the students. Results revealed a significant difference in the test scores when both groups were compared. Therefore, using Zoom technology as a learning platform was efficacious for students to elevate their pronunciation skills. Students, however, have positive feedback to its assistance in their pronunciation Henceforth, the study concluded that Zoom technology effectively taught Arabic pronunciation at Dar Ashifa'a Qur'aan Learning School. Further implications were discovered and discussed.

Keywords: Pronunciation, Arabic, Zoom technology, Distance Education, Technology, Arabic Learners, Classical Arabic

INTRODUCTION

This chapter presented the background of the study, its problems, hypothesis, theoretical framework, conceptual paradigm, scope and delimitations, significance, and definition of terms.

Learning a foreign language requires four skills: reading, listening, writing, and speaking. Speaking a language accurately is to pronounce the words correctly. Many students are having challenges pronouncing

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the words of the foreign language. One of those interesting languages is the Arabic language. People worldwide are eager to learn this unique language as some grew up in the Middle East, it is a job requirement, or some are just interested in exploring Middle Eastern culture. As for the Muslims, it is required for them, as this is part of their religion to implement in their Islamic practices and prayers. Learners grow increasingly around the globe, but not all can easily access and practice speaking the language. In that case, the discovery of the technology was used to accommodate what students needed and wanted. One of the technology tools used to learn Arabic pronunciation is Zoom. Teachers and students can interact with each other through Zoom Technology in learning Arabic Pronunciation.

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The importance of language cannot be underestimated because it is the vehicle of thought and communication. N. Guzacheva, (2020). One of the essential language learning skills is pronunciation because it makes communication possible. (Islam Ababneh, 2018). Pronunciation is one of the fundamentals of oral communication; it is a significant factor in learning a language. As Yi Fang (2022) stated, pronunciation is accepted as one of the essential elements that help people feel confident when they communicate and get their message across effectively. Pronunciation training improves speaking abilities by assisting the learners to develop clear speaking skills. (Darcy, 2018). Prashant (2018) articulates that effective communication in any language is believed to emerge with proper pronunciation, which helps in further understanding the association and use of words. Without the sound (the phonology or the pronunciation), one cannot bring the rest of language to life (Darcy, 2018). Proper pronunciation also encourages learners to use the target language more frequently and confidently (Yi Fang, 2022). Therefore, pronunciation is an essential part of communication, and without correct pronunciation, nobody can talk about the existence of efficient communication (Nurcihan Yürük. 2020). Thus, good pronunciation means being understood. (Yulduz, 2021).

Pronunciation in Arabic language is critical in learning the language. Learning Classical Arabic, the language of the Qur'an is it is essential for Muslims worldwide because it is used for prayer, Qur'anic recitations, and other religious practices. As Ahlam Wahdan, Sendeyah Hantoobi, Said A. Salloum, Khaled Shaalan, 2020 stated, Arabic is one of the six primary languages worldwide. Its use is spread across many countries worldwide, and it is the basis of the Arab world. Some Islamic countries also use Arabic as their primary language because it is the language of the Quran. The Holy Qur'an was revealed in Arabic. Allah (S. W. T) says: "Indeed, we have made it an Arabic Qur'an that you will comprehend." [Al-Qur'an 43:3] The above-quoted verse in the Holy Qur'an shows that the Arabic language is not merely a language of the Arabs but a language of all that must be learned to understand Islam. (Solaiman 2017). According to Fatma Yousuf Al Busaidi (2019), learning Arabic as a foreign language (AFL) is increasing worldwide.

Even so, non-native speakers of Arabic face an array of communication difficulties. Learning how to pronounce a language correctly is one of the most challenging aspects of learning a new

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language, and it is also one of the least popular subjects for instructors to handle in the classroom (Darcy, 2018). Technology is one of the tools for learning a foreign language. According to James Francis (2017), technology has been increasingly integrated into daily life; today's generation of learners has grown up with technology all around them, where access to a vast collection of information is only a fingertip away. Thus, teachers and students were forced to participate in modernization, and teachers had to adapt to this new lifestyle (James Francis, 2017). Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic forced colleges and universities to move from in-person courses to online learning (Hodges, Moore, Lockee, Trust, & Bond, 2020). Therefore, when the effects of technology on foreign language learning and teaching are considered, the critical role of technology cannot be neglected (Yürük, 2019). Zoom Technology is one of the tools used in learning Arabic Pronunciation. As (Lederman, 2020a, 2020b) mentioned, it is not unexpected that many academics chose to use Zoom technology and other web conferencing platforms to conduct classes.

The learning of Arabic as a foreign language (AFL) is increasing around the world. As Jaafar (2018) stated, Arabic is the world's fifth most widely spoken language, with 422 million speakers, and has undergone significant developments not only in the Arab region but also in non-Arab countries. Learning how to pronounce a language correctly is one of the most challenging aspects of learning a new language, and it is also one of the least popular subjects for instructors to handle in the classroom (Darcy, 2018). Hence, learners of Arabic face several obstacles that limit their communicative competence and delay their attainment of proficiency. As Nassima Kerras and Moulay Lahssan Baya Essayahi (2022) stated, even under normal conditions, studying the Arabic language is an immense challenge for students. Non-native speakers learners of Arabic face an array of communication difficulties (Fatma Yousuf Al-Busaidi1, 2019). According to Fatma Yousuf Al-Busaidil (2019), pronunciation-related issues are one of the distinct difficulties when the student attempts to communicate in Arabic. Many researchers contend that foreign adult learners of Arabic are likely to experience pronunciation difficulties that cause communication breakdown or hinder speech intelligibility (Shehata, 2017). Hence, the already-daunting challenge of learning Arabic is intensified even further when adding the COVID-19 complications and online learning to the equation. (Nassima Kerras and Moulay LahssanBaya Essayahi, 2022). In addition, high levels of accuracy

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in pronunciation are frequently difficult to achieve for non-native speakers. For those who teach Islam and are visibly the leaders of Islam or aspire to these positions, their pronunciation of classical Arabic must be impeccable. Hence, according to Afrianto (2018; Angelianawati (2019), some foreign language practitioners have studied topics related to English, the use of social media in English language teaching (Anggraeni, 2018), and the utilization of mobile applications to support language teaching (Halimah, Ibrahim, & Lustyantje, 2018). However, compared with the studies on teaching other foreign languages, mainly English, those on the Arabic language are fewer. In addition, according to Yürük, N. (2020), pronunciation is one of the main problems in language teaching and learning, and it gets little attention. Most second language learners underestimate the importance of pronunciation, considering that pronunciation is less important than other aspects of language. For these reasons, looking for and using various communicative and interactive tools helps capture and maintain the student's attention and cannot be underestimated. Rapanta et al. (2020) explain: "Online learning and teaching involve making use of a diverse an array of tools, resources, pedagogical approaches, roles, organizational arrangements and forms of interaction, monitoring, and support—with many possible combinations of substitution and integration". Therefore, Zoom technology is a learning tool for Arabic Language learners.

Zoom is a collaborative, cloud-based videoconferencing service offering features including online meetings, group messaging services, and secure session recording; as HyeJeong Kim (2020) stated, Zoom is an interactive audio and video program based on Cloud technology. Programs that were once used primarily for inter-company video. As with comparable platforms like Skype, Zoom offers the ability to communicate in real-time with geographically dispersed individuals via computer, tablet, or mobile device (Mandy M. Archibald et al., 2019). Even though the classes are done by videoconference, thus allowing the students to practice, ask, and interact with the teacher and classmates live, the computer screen creates an additional, unwanted obstacle, as Octavio (2021).

This study, the primary aim of this research is to see the effect of zoom technology among Arabic language learners and if this study can contribute to Arabic Language instruction in pronunciation skills.

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Research Questions :

1. What are the students' feedback on using zoom in teaching Arabic pronunciation?
2. Is there a significant posttest gain in the Arabic pronunciation skills of students after being exposed to zoom-based platform?
3. Is there a significant difference in the Arabic pronunciation skills between the control and experimental group?
4. What are the features of using zoom technology as a learning platform that influenced the performance of Arabic language students?
5. What is the instructional materials maybe proposed based on findings?

Null Hypothesis

H_0 : There was no significant difference between Zoom technology as learning platform pre-test and post-test scores.

H_a : There was a significant difference between Zoom technology as learning platform pre-test and post-test scores.

H_0 : Non-Zoom technology was not significantly different as a learning platform pre-test and post-test scores.

H_a : There was a significant difference between Non- Zoom technology as learning platform pre-test and post-test scores.

H_0 : There was no significant difference between non-Zoom technology and Zoom technology pre-test and post-test scores.

H_a : There was a significant difference between non-Zoom technology and Zoom technology pre-test and post-test scores.

Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework is a logically developed and connected set of concepts and premises— designed from one or more theories—that a researcher creates to scaffold a study (Varpio, Lara et al., 2019). The researcher must define all theories and concepts that will provide the grounding of the research, connecting them logically, and relating these concepts to the study being conducted to develop a theoretical framework.

This research applied the Connectivism theory, a new learning theory

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typically used for online learning (Corbett and Spinello, 2020). In the connectivist approach, the learner embraces knowledge as a network, with the help of Zoom technology, develops mental connections between pieces of information during interaction with various information sources. (Olga Dziubaniuk et. al 2023). The principles of connectivism may help instructors create a learning environment where Arabic Language learners can improve their pronunciation skills through online interactions and by accessing digital knowledge sources.

Connectivism describes the link between human learning and the pervasive access to knowledge made possible by the current technological environment (Frederique Corbett, Elio Spinello, 2020). Connectivism is occasionally described as "a learning theory for a digital age," as George Siemens (2004) did (Stephen Downes, 2022). Connectivism was first discussed by George Siemens in a seminal online article initially written on December 12, 2004, and then revised on April 5, 2005, where he called it "a learning theory for the digital age". (Frederique Corbett , Elio Spinello, 2020). According to Corbet and Spinello (2020), George Siemens firmly anchored his theory against other traditional learning theories, which he described as inadequate in the face of new and revolutionary social networking technologies affecting searching, research, teaching, learning, and numerous other aspects of daily life. Siemens (2005) notes that "over the last twenty years, technology has reorganized how we live, communicate, and learn. Learning needs and theories describing learning principles and processes should reflect underlying social environments." Henceforth, from its early beginnings, connectivism was subsequently positioned as a learning theory alternative more in line with the evolving environment and the logical and natural response to significant technological shifts affecting learning. Connectivism theory is determined by the understanding that decisions are made in a dynamic environment with continually changing information. Furthermore, Having the capacity to know more beyond what is known today is a vital principle of connectivism. In addition, the main coordinates of the new theory are the possibility to establish connections between ideas, domains, and concepts and the freedom to choose one's own information. According to connectivism, knowledge can be stored in several digital formats and distributed in an information network (Alina Sirghea, 2020).

According to Corbet and Spinello (2020), connectivism examines technology trends, the evolution of learning, changes in organizations, and the nature and source of knowledge. The basis for knowledge creation is networking, according to connectivism. Individuals connect to nodes from a more extensive, diversified network and share internal information with a learning community. Learning is defined by connectivism as a networked group effort in which connecting people and information sources is the learning process.

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(Frederique Corbett , Elio Spinello, 2020) According to Gavin Hendricks (2019), connectivism emphasizes that learning takes place in various networks and that the learner plays a crucial role in knowledge creation due to the social construction of knowledge. Furthermore, connectivism is the idea that information is spread over a network of connections and that learning is the process of building and navigating those networks. In this learning environment, students can connect to the network and create their learning. Unlike the methods and theories of traditional learning like cognitivism (where learning is an active, constructive process), behaviorism (a theory of learning based on the idea that all behaviors are acquired through conditioning) or constructivism (the theory that humans construct knowledge and meaning from their experiences), with connectivism, learning is defined by connections to a network of expertise that can include any form of interaction. Additionally, enthusiastic practitioners who applied connectivism to Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) greatly aided in the validity of its merits and its acceptability as a helpful learning theory. In universities, using digital technologies to set up the learning environment has evolved into "the new normal" and may even be more used in the future to bridge online and offline learning. Digital teaching abilities and student assistance must be given top attention in the pedagogy of online teaching as online learning is further integrated into the foundations of higher education (Kordrostami & Seitz, 2022; Simamora, 2020). Years ago, while the ideas of connectivism may have been radical, surprising, controversial, and a little ambiguous, today their merits are better understood if not increasingly accepted. According to AIDahdouh (2018), the theory of connectivism can be helpful in the design of the learning environment. Connectivism learning theory can be a suitable alternative in cases where students develop knowledge by forming social networks with the help of technology. Dunaway (2011) stated, "Connectivism acknowledges the role of information technology in accessing information from multiple sources and developing skills for evaluating connections between different sources in a dynamic information network." Thus, connectivism aids in identifying the enablers of learning and are brought about by advances in technology and the design of an appropriate learning environments. According to Stephen Downes (2018), Siemens' Eight Principles of the Connectivism Learning Theory: Principle 1: Learning and Knowledge Rests in Diversity of Opinions: The Internet allows anyone a voice and an opinion on any given topic. Using Zoom technology, the students can develop intercultural skills by sharing engaging materials such as videos, articles, and presentations. (N. Guzacheva 2020). Principle 2: Learning is a Process of Connecting Specialized Nodes or Information Sources: When data is free and open, discoveries are always around the corner. A core literacy skill of today is connecting information

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sources to get a new or more complete view of any subject. Zoom is used to explore how videoconferencing can help learners develop their communicative competence (HyeJeong Kim, 2020). Principle 3: Learning May Reside in Non-human Appliances: According to Jeff Utecht (2019), in every classroom today, educators are faced with looking at the backs of devices instead of their students' faces. Principle 4: Capacity to Know More is More Critical than What is Currently Known: Teachers now have the vital task of educating students on conducting profound research utilizing all the available resources. This includes exposing them to content available through library databases and Internet searches (Jeff Utecht, 2019). In Zoom, Arabic language teachers can cater to each student's proficiency level and learning goals by delivering different online resources to individual students so they can work on them independently (N. Guzacheva 2020). Principle 5: Nurturing and Maintaining Connections is Needed to Facilitate Continual Learning: A new era of collaboration is here. Collaboration in the modern sense of the word means face-to-face collaboration and collaboration across time and space. According to N. Guzacheva (2020), Zoom is a great pedagogical tool for collaboration. Principle 6: Ability to See Connections between Fields, Ideas, and Concepts is a Core Skill: Peer-to-peer and face-to-face interaction is vital to the education process. Using Zoom's 'breakout room' function; teachers can create opportunities for students to use the language productively, produce meaning-focused output, and engage in student-to-student interaction (González-Lloret, 2020). Principle 7: Currency (accurate, up-to-date knowledge) is the Intent of all Connectivist Learning Activities. Learning requires using these new search tools in a connected, quick-changing world of information (Jeff Utecht, 2019). Principle 8: Decision-making is a Learning Process: For example, through Zoom, the educator screen-shared video about the topic, and students understand all of the information and then choose which video to watch. It is a skill practiced to maximize learning.

In conclusion, in this study, connectivism is a theoretical framework for understanding learning, where learners "make connections between ideas located throughout their personal learning networks, which are composed of numerous information resources and technologies" (Dunaway, 2011). A connective theory is a general framework for online activities where learners acquire listening and speaking skills by implementing these activities; students cooperate and interact with each other via Zoom technology to develop their pronunciation skills. Mohammed (2005) pointed out that there is no ideal approach to teaching the Arabic language because each of the available methods has both advantages and disadvantages. Hence, students use

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technologies to form their information networks, including learning communities in which students participate in the knowledge creation process rather than merely consuming information. The recognized advantages of technology in language teaching are generally not language-specific but share common features across languages, including the acquisition of Arabic pronunciation. Therefore, this paper seeks to examine the effect of Zoom technology on the learning process of Arabic language students in terms of their pronunciation.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1.

Conceptual Framework of the study

As illustrated on the graph, the researchers' input was the intervention of Zoom technology in Arabic language classrooms, particularly in the Zoom Technology group. The following graph comprised the processes needed to collect the data. Numerical data were gathered via pre-test and post-test in the non-zoom technology and Zoom technology groups. Moreover, verbal data were it was accumulated via interview on the Zoom technology group only. The final graph depicted the output of the researchers after conducting such a process, whether using Zoom technology improved students' pronunciation

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skills in the Arabic language.

Scope and Delimitations

This study has limitations as the topic was limited to sounds of Arabic, as pronounced only by beginner students at Dar Ashifa'a Qur'aan Learning School. Only fifty Filipino participants participated in this research. Time-Limit: The period is undertaken for six weeks.

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Significance of the Study

Through this research, the use of Zoom application, which in the beginning was created to communicate can now be beneficial for an educational purpose by: Teachers and Educators: it can help them bring their students together in a frictionless environment to get more done. (N. Guzacheva 2020). Furthermore, it allows teachers to explore and assess their student's skills. Zoom motivates to annotate their shared screen, making lessons more interactive. They can record their lessons and watch them again to assess students' strengths and weaknesses. (N. Guzacheva, 2020). Instructors will be able to create improved plans for online classes by understanding the efficiency, strengths, and weaknesses of real-time remote video classes as well as considering their complementary aspects, in addition, according to HyeJeong Kim (2020), communication tools such as Zoom can help educational providers manage, plan, deliver, and track students' learning processes.

Students: In some areas with limited mobility access and a limited number of Arabic Language teachers, the students can now access and learn using Zoom. They can develop intercultural skills by sharing engaging materials such as videos, articles, and presentations. Moreover, they can analyze and evaluate their learning and self-assess their skills by watching recorded lessons. They can watch the recorded lessons sequentially to see their improvement over time. (N. Guzacheva 2020). Zoom is used to explore how videoconferencing can help learners develop their communicative competence HyeJeong Kim, (2020).

Curriculum / Instruction: can provide easier access to course resources. Offer greater convenience and flexibility in scheduling for the Arabic language teacher and student. HyeJeong Kim, (2020). It can be personalized – that is, Arabic language teachers can cater to each student's proficiency level and learning goals by delivering different online resources to individual students so they can work on them in their own time (N. Guzacheva 2020).

This research can help develop advanced systems that can effectively facilitate Second Language learning with accurate

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pronunciation, and it may provide new methods of learning that will assist the instructor in developing and treating pronunciation difficulties. Even if online distance learning cannot completely replace traditional learning methods, it can facilitate learning or provide more effective solutions.

Definition of Terms

Al-Qaai'dah An-Nooraniyyah: a book that means acquiring the skills of hearing, pronunciation, reading, and writing in the Arabic language (Furqan Center).

Arabic is one of the six primary languages worldwide. Its use is spread across many countries in the world, and it is the basis of the Arab world, but some Islamic countries also use the Arabic language as their primary language because it is the language of the Qur'an (Wahdan, Ahlam, et al., 2020).

Beginner Arabic learners: Arabic students who learn the basic Arabic language. They are the students who learn Arabic for the first time (Alimin, Alimin, et al., 2021).

Classical Arabic: is the language of the Holy Quran) and is still used largely in religious context and studies despite being more than 1400 years old (Ali, A. et al.'s, 2021).

Distance Education: is a formal education where the learning group is separated, and where interactive telecommunications systems are used to connect learners, resources, and instructors (Clark, 2020).

Holy Qur'an: is a sacred book where it is not permissible to modify, add, or move any of the letters or any diacritical mark to it (Mahdi, M. S. 2023).

Modern Standard Arabic (MSA): is a modified version of Classical Arabic currently used in everyday communication in Arabic speaking countries (Ziafat, N. et. al. 2021).

Pronunciation: is a process of mastering reading skills that begins with studying the sound system of language, various kinds of vocabulary, and sentence structures (Nabilah et. al 2021).

Technology: is the most abundant and clearly defined element of online learning (Singh, V., & Thurman, A., 2019).

Zoom Technology: Zoom is a video conferencing tool you can use to meet with others online - either by video or audio-only or both, all while conducting live chats - and it lets you record those sessions to view later

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(N. Guzacheva, 2020).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Review of related literature in any field of investigation has become an inevitable part of research work. The relevant studies and literature that the researcher had gathered and carefully examined were presented in this chapter.

CONCEPTUAL LITERATURE.

Pronunciation skills

Pronunciation is a general term that includes several distinct features present in human languages. According to Yi Fang (2022), learning a second language comes with a fair share of difficulties for second language learners. One such difficulty is pronunciation, which may be brought about by factors such as mother tongue interference and different language sound systems. The correct pronunciation skill is hard and challenging to measure because there is no universal definition for correctness in the context of human languages, but there has been some research in this domain (Huang, H.; Xu, H.; Hu, Y.; Zhou, G., 2017). Krishnasamy and Mello (2017,) point out that although pronunciation receives the least attention in classrooms for English learners, it is the most crucial aspect when it comes to an understanding of what a person says when they are speaking a language. Understandable pronunciation is an essential component of communicative competence. Thus, good pronunciation means being understood (Yulduz, 2021).

Pronunciation is one of the basic requirements of learner's competence and it also requires a place in language instruction. Learners' pronunciation levels play a significant role in language learning because it may promote or hinder language learning process (Pourhosein, 2016). During instruction process, learners should be provided with courses and materials that help them improve their pronunciation. According to Yürük, N. (2020), pronunciation is an essential part of communication and without correct pronunciation nobody can talk about the existence of efficient communication. In foreign language

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classes the focus is generally on grammar and vocabulary and this makes learners become skillful in listening and reading. Pronunciation is learnt by repeating sounds and correcting them when produced inaccurately. When learners start learning pronunciation they make new habits and overcome the difficulties resulting from the first language.

With this in mind, teachers should set obtainable goals that are applicable and suitable for the communication needs of learners. Pronunciation instruction has to aim at intelligible pronunciation and teachers can actively encourage their learners' actual production, build pronunciation awareness and practice. Pronunciation instruction is very important because it is the main source of understanding. If learners cannot utter the correct version of a word then they are not able to communicate correctly. Pronunciation instruction helps learners to have a better understanding of native speakers and improves their ability to communicate easily and effectively.

According to Abbas Hussein and Syed Farhat Jahara (2021), the best way to comprehend people is to listen to them carefully to improve one's pronunciation. Therefore, pronunciation plays a vital role in learning a language as oral language skills are the foundation of literacy acquisition (Snow, 2020).

According to Nurcihan Yürük (2019), teaching pronunciation is prominent in foreign language teaching. In spite of this, pronunciation has somehow become the most neglected and excluded component of language teaching and learning. Moreover, in the field of Arabic Foreign Language studies, very little is known and very little research has been conducted regarding Arabic pronunciation (Shehata, 2017).

Arabic language teaching

Arabic language is the fifth widely used language in the world and there are around 422 million speakers of Arabic as their first language on the globe (Julian, G. 2020). In the broader term, Arabic language can be categorized into Classical Arabic (CA) and modern standard Arabic (MSA) dialects. MSA is a modified version of CA currently used in everyday communication in Arabic speaking countries. Classical Arabic is the

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language of the Holy Quran (Ali, A. et al., 2021) and is still used largely in religious context and studies despite being more than 1400 years old. The Holy Qur'an was revealed in Arabic. Allah (S. W. T) says: "Indeed We have made it an Arabic Qur'an that perchance you will comprehend." [Al-Qur'an 43:3] The above quoted verse in the Holy Qur'an shows that the Arabic language is not merely a language of the Arabs but a language of all that must be learnt to understand Islam. (Solaiman 2017). According to Ibrahim Al-Huri(2015), the Arabic language is one of the world's leading languages with more than 300 million native speakers in 22 Arab countries, where Arabic is the official language.

According to Al-Marri, M et al.'s (2018), in the Arabic language, the accurate pronunciation of phonemes is required in learning the language to void change in the meaning of the sentence. In many countries around the world, the Classical Arabic is part of the schools' syllabus. Correct pronunciation of phonemes as per defined rules is an essential requirement to preserve the meaning of the words. Mispronunciation results in two types of errors; firstly, it changes the meaning of the word completely. Secondly, it defies the rules of pronunciation, and both errors are forbidden in Classical Arabic. As Arafa, M.N.M. et al.'s (2018) stated, learning the correct pronunciation of Arabic alphabets is challenging, and it requires each learner to follow an individual teacher, who listens and corrects the mistakes separately for each learner. When speaking Classical Arabic, the speakers tend to produce all the sounds according to the existing rules for Classical Arabic pronunciation. According to Ziafat, N. et al.'s (2021), Classical Arabic has precise and explicitly defined rules for correct pronunciation to conserve the accurate meaning of the words and provides a framework to facilitate both the natives and non-natives learning the language. These rules are standardized, widely available, and recognized by the Arabic speaking world (Czerepinski, K). In Classical Arabic, alphabets' articulation points and characteristics and massive practicing of vocals play a significant role in correct pronunciation. According to Amna Asif et al.'s (2022), in a typical Classical Arabic learning institute, a single teacher may be responsible for listening to and correcting the mistakes of several dozen learners on a single day. This is quite a laborious job leading to fatigue and is prone to diminished error correction by the instructor over time. Moreover, each student has to wait for their turn to speak or read the learned parts. If this job can be helped by letting the students' work with their pronunciation using technology, it will improve the efficiency of the

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learning process and the overall productivity of the students and instructors. Moreover, this will open new ways of distant and home-based learning with the presence of an instructor. As learning can take place anytime and anywhere, the teacher can detect pronunciation errors and give feedback to the learner. It is worth mentioning that in the Arabic language, the correct pronunciation is vital and requires a lot of practice by the learner of the language. Currently, the students not only rely on in-class participation but also practice using digital technology. In this regard, we have evidence of the development of many applications supporting the students' learning process. There is a need for research in developing systems and applications for improving Arabic reading and speaking knowledge. In various parts of the world when there is an unavailability of real teachers, such applications play an important role in supporting the student's learning process. The Arabic-speaking countries are a recent place of interest for many tourists around the world. Therefore, many people are interested to learn this language for their survival in this part of the world. Any developed technology or application will be beneficial for people who want to learn Arabic using the available online resources (Amna Asif et al.'s 2022).

Its use is spread across many countries in the world, and it is the basis of the Arab world, but some Islamic countries also use the Arabic language as their primary language because it is the language of the Qur'an. The Arabic language consists of 28 letters (Said A. Salloum , 2022). In Arabic, a mispronunciation of Arabic short vowels can change the meaning of a complete sentence (Amna Asif, Hamid Mukhtar, Fatimah Alqadheeb, Hafiz Farooq Ahmad and Abdulaziz Alhumam, 2022).

Hassan Alhuzali, Mohamed Elaraby (2018), the term Arabic itself refers to a collection of varieties, possibly comprised by these major categories: (1) Modern Standard Arabic (MSA), (2) Classical Arabic (CA), and (3) Dialectal Arabic (DA) which is also called Colloquial Arabic. Arabic has become a scientific and academic language, as well as a popular language in the international community. Thus, using Arabic to convey scientific truths is important (Bulkisah, 2017). The potential for the development and uses of the Arabic language in various fields of life (social, economic, business, tourism, politics, culture, and others) remains large and wide open. As a consequence, the quality of Arabic language teaching needs greater improvement so that Arabic language learners can be professionally competitive in the current industrialized era (Arifin,

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2018).

A major aim for Arabic language teaching is to enable learners to communicate linguistically whether orally or in writing. The modern view of teaching is different than it was before regarding the role of both the student and the learner in the education process. The new role of the teacher requires the use of different teaching methods that meet the various needs of the students)Nahla

A. K. Alhirtani, 2019). Scholars and researchers agree that the quality of teachers is one of the keys to the students' success in academic (Robert Vagi, et.al 2019). According to W. Ye & W. Law (2019), the reality shows that the teachers mostly concern about how to ensure and improve the students' achievement in learning processes. Hence, the teachers play the main role in educational development, especially those that are conducted formally in schools .

In addition, Azkia Muharom Albantani Ahmad and Madkur (2019) stated that educational policy plays a pivotal role in Arabic language instruction. The existence of an Arabic language learning program and its development in a school reflects how the educational institution leads this program toward an effective direction. Despite the fact that some previous research studies (e.g., El Omari & Bataineh, 2018; Hamidin, 2019; and Poyas and Bawardi, 2018) have explored the difficulties faced by learners of Arabic, and a critical review of these studies indicates a pressing need for further studies. For instance, according to Fatma Yousuf Al Busaidi (2019), the research works have studied difficulties in general but have yet to focus on communication-related difficulties, mainly speaking. The researcher's learning and teaching experience of Arabic language pronunciation sparks the interest to explore the different methods of teaching and learning the language in pronunciation. One of the ways is the use of technology.

Technology embraces language learning

According to Blake (2017), technology significantly impacts the design and implementation of education. It can be integrated in different ways in language learning environments, ranging from being a communication tool to being a virtual student tutor. Teaching second languages online using technology has now become standard.

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Technological development and digital transformation have facilitated the delivery of online courses via remote learning (Dietrich et al., 2020). Hence, the result of the study conducted by Nousiainen et al. (2018) showed that in the digitalization era, teachers should be able to integrate technology with pedagogy and develop active classrooms to promote cooperative interaction. Moreover, the teachers should have professional standards by mastering the materials and teaching strategies encourage students to study hard.

The research by Aggrawal and Chakraborty (2019) explains the helpfulness of CAPT in learning English among Chinese students. A study by Wang (2017) explains the effectiveness of social media applications such as WeChat in China to improve the pronunciation of learners. According to Wang (2017), the introduction of technology and digital media platforms such as WeChat encourages self-learning and enhances learning flexibility. The support functions of WeChat can help users solve pronunciation difficulties in English. Integrating computer-based learning helps students conduct and learn the application of the English language in a practical day-to-day experience. The study by Wang concluded that the entertainment value associated with the social media application is a great means of attracting students' attention. Moreover, a foreign language practitioner has studied topics related to English (Afrianto, 2018; Angelianawati, 2019), the use of social media in English language teaching (Anggraeni, 2018), and the utilization of mobile applications to support language teaching (Halimah, Ibrahim, & Lustyantje, 2018).

However, compared with the studies on teaching other foreign languages, particularly English, those on the Arabic language are fewer. Among them was produced by Amna Asif et al.'s (2022) study. Their research is to develop a classification system for correct and incorrect pronunciation of the Arabic short vowels. It is novel research focusing on the subtle pronunciation differences in Arabic speech processing. The outcomes of this research can be useful in developing advanced systems that can autonomously classify words and sentences to facilitate CA learning with accurate pronunciation effectively. As there are 28 alphabets in the Arabic language and each alphabet has three possible vowel states, they make a total of 84 unique phonemes.

Also, the study of Wildana Wargadinataa et al. (2020) discovered a shift in Arabic learning by UIN Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang students

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from personal to instrumental due to the current COVID-19 pandemic situation. In this case, there was a transformation in Arabic learning from a personal-cultural approach to an instrumental-functional approach. This research has implications regarding the ideal Arabic learning process in the conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic. The shift also took place in the degree of teachers' dependence towards dependence on technology during the pandemic situation. The result shows that most students use the WhatsApp application and most study autonomously through online platforms. A study conducted by Taufiq Urrochman (2019) found that Arabic electronic dictionaries are beneficial for supporting present-day language instruction and, therefore, a lexicology course needs to be developed by instilling teaching materials that examine electronic dictionaries.

In addition, Plumb and LaRosa (2017) stated that online games are educational applications that depend on student response systems, and they are up-to-date technologies with some advantages, including being free, easy, and engaging. Teachers can use them to create three types of activities: quizzes, discussions, and surveys. Also, they do not require students to create an account to participate in any kind of activities because teachers do that. They are compatible with any smartphone, tablet, or computer, give instant feedback, and improve the students' excitement and engagement. Online games also have some advantages for teachers. They help instructors when they want to download, review, and save learners' results, and they can create quizzes, discussion questions, and surveys, and it also helps in adjusting the response time (Plumb & LaRosa, 2017).

Online games can help students and learners create a new way of assessing their knowledge. These games with different types of activities such as quizzes, discussions and surveys can create an increase in the students' attitudes towards what they learn as well as their participation in the class and the learning process as a whole (Omar, 2017). Therefore, technology embrace language learning. Thus, the integration of digital tools with learning a new language is helpful for learners to grasp the contents quickly.

Ignorance of how to handle the technicalities of online learning has also plagued learning the Arabic language. Computer skills are a necessary skill For online learning most students and teachers need more. However,

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there is no room for computer illiteracy (Abuhammad, 2020). Educators and students are expected to possess these skills and have some knowledge of web usage, search, and online chatting to qualify for e-learning programs. A lack of these skills can significantly impact the submission of various online assignments or tests and online evaluations, which are indispensable elements of e-learning (Abuhammad, 2020). Despite the challenges hindering online learning, many previous studies indicated that technology positively influences language learning (Fendler, 2021). Hence, technology has been used in learning for some time (Alqarni, Bown, Pullen, & Maters, 2020).

Online programs have played a part in interactive education and virtual learning programs that have typically gone through a formal method of developing a virtual classroom, introducing it to students, and building a committed framework for supporting school-enrolled learners (Cleveland-Innes & Garrison, 2020; Ray, 2020). In online learning or e-learning, multimedia resources are used to access the educational program beyond the standard classroom. According to Paudel (2021), online language teaching and learning programs have increased in many educational environments worldwide due to recent interest in online education. Therefore, online distance learning tools are changing our world and how we learn to live.

Zoom as a pedagogical tool

One of the new original software-based conference room solutions is Zoom technology (N. Guzacheva, 2020). Today's language learners are used to incorporating technology into the learning experience and expect opportunities to engage and interact (Kessler, 2018). Educators may not be fully prepared to teach online in real time as it requires new digital competencies (Starkey, 2020). One such competency is utilizing and maximizing Synchronous Meeting Tools like Zoom. This tech review explores some of the challenges language educators experience with synchronous online teaching and suggests ways that Zoom can help address them (Lucas Kohnke and Benjamin Luke Moorhouse, 2020). The Zoom program allows for synchronous interactions between educators and students.

According to Rahayu (2020), in this online environment, individuals use a webcam and a microphone to chat in real time, enabling

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interactions similar to those in the traditional classroom setting. Up to 200 individuals can participate in live sessions, and an additional 3000 attendees can passively view the session (Dharma et al. 2017). According to N. Guzacheva (2020), Zoom is an excellent pedagogical tool for collaboration. Medical students can use the chat box with another learner, their English teacher, or the group. They can see everyone's camera and listen to everyone. English teachers can use the breakout rooms to group learners in pairs, threes, or in whatever size group they want. It's a great way to encourage pair or group work and allow medical students to work independently. From Guzacheva N.'s experience as an online English teacher, Zoom has become an indispensable technology for the way they work, teach, and learn together. Zoom has the capability of hosting 100 participants at a time, including audio and video. The platform is designed so that even with limited bandwidth, it works well. With Zoom's continued improvement in new features, they are excited to continue to find new and creative ways to create social presence in our classrooms of medical education. To sum up, with the technology brought by Zoom, medical students will forget that their English teacher is a few thousand miles away from them. The innovative approach of Zoom technology enhances positive learning outcomes for diverse groups of medical students as well as encouraging higher education in remote areas while potentially reducing workloads for English teachers.

Learners can participate in a variety of different educational activities within the Zoom environment. For example, communication-related activities include greeting others, classroom lectures, question and answers and group discussions in breakout rooms (Rahayu 2020). . According to Lucas Kohnke and Benjamin Luke Moorhouse (2020), educators have utilized a range of online synchronous meeting tools (SMTs) to facilitate student learning. One of the popular, immersive and easy-to-use SMTs is Zoom. It includes several features, such as annotation tools, polls, breakout rooms and video and screen sharing. These functions facilitate communicative language learning through the use of authentic language instruction in interactive synchronous classes.. Activities related to materials comprise sharing slides or screens with students or educators, downloading homework assignments and uploading answers to questions (Rahayu 2020).

Activities related to studying can take the form of answering polling questions, presenting lessons using slides or the whiteboard,

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classroom practice using the whiteboard or chat box and group work in breakout rooms (Rahayu 2020). Students and educators can also meet individually to discuss the student's work, and these sessions can be recorded for viewing later (McClendon et al. 2017). Therefore, The electronic educational resource Zoom has helped to introduce a number of innovations into foreign language instruction (N. Guzacheva, 2020).

Zoom allows students to indicate through non-verbal icons when they have a question, show agreement or indicate if they want the teacher to speed up, slow down or take a break . These icons can provide useful information regarding students' attentiveness, excitement, agreement or confusion with the language content being presented. Nonverbal functions also allow the teacher to provide corrective feedback Wang (2017). If the students have a query beyond those represented by 'icons', they can use the written chat function to ask a question privately or to the whole class. This can be particularly useful for learners who are afraid to show their confusion to the whole class or are nervous about their oral English.

According to Lucas Kohnke and Benjamin Luke Moorhouse (2020), These modes of participation can aid students in developing their communicative competencies, as they need to select the most appropriate method to get their message across to the teacher and class. Depending on classroom discipline, 'student-to-student' and 'send to all' chats can be disabled while still maintaining a non-verbal private link between students and the teacher. Most SMTs allow for lecture-style sessions where the teacher provides monologues with little student interaction. This is mainly due to synchronous group work being harder to integrate and monitor on most platforms.

Through using Zoom's 'breakout room' function, teachers can create opportunities for students to use language productively, produce meaning- focused output, and engage in student-to-student interaction. Meaning-focused output and student-to-student interaction are crucial to successful language learning (González-Lloret, 2020). For example, students can be placed in small groups or pairs within a session to engage in spoken language practice, discussions, and roleplays. In addition, when combined with other tools such as Google Forms and Google Docs, students can co-construct texts and complete language

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exercises in groups. This negotiation of meaning is 'an important factor for successful L2 acquisition' as students are pushed to process language output (Irati de Nicolás Saiz Ariane Sande Piñeiro, 2022).

Teachers can assign students different roles to ensure they remain focused, with someone nominated to share their product with the whole class. If students want additional time to complete group tasks, this can be indicated using the clock icon. Teachers can broadcast messages to the rooms, enter the rooms to monitor tasks, and bring students back into the main meeting. Teachers may struggle to keep learners engaged during a longer live online session. To address this, Zoom allows the teacher to integrate polls and surveys that can be used to engage learners and gather answers, perceptions, and ideas from the class. These tools can be used for formative assessment – serving as entry and exit tickets to gauge what students already know about the content, or for the teacher to check students' understanding before moving on.

In addition, they can be useful for conducting language-focused exercises with right or wrong answers, as the answer can be directly displayed, giving feedback to students and teachers on student understanding, and can be a catalyst for elaboration on linguistic features. Zoom allows teachers and students to share browser screens synchronously, so teachers can incorporate student response systems, such as Mentimeter and GoSoapBox, to leverage the interactive environment and facilitate active learning (Moorhouse and Kohnke, 2020; Kohnke, 2019). For example, teachers could elicit vocabulary using a word cloud. Teachers can also play videos and audio files for meaning-focused input and receptive listening practice activities. To substitute a physical classroom whiteboard, Zoom includes several annotation tools through its 'screen share' and 'whiteboard' functions (e.g. text box, freeform draw/ pen, stamps, shapes, and highlighter) that teachers can use to check student understanding. These are particularly helpful for learners to notice the mismatch between their language production and the target form Irati de Nicolás Saiz Ariane Sande Piñeiro (2022). For example, the teacher can highlight cohesive devices in an essay, explain a grammatical concept, or ask students to use the stamp feature to indicate parts of speech or underline stress in two-syllable words. These tools can be used in a whole class setting and 'breakout rooms' by both students and teachers, promote participation, and language production, and reduce anxiety. The built-in recording and transcription functions allow teachers to record the entire or short

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sections of a session, e.g. grammar presentations, assessment reviews, or homework instructions for students who miss a class or want to review the lesson later. Students can be encouraged to take greater ownership of their language learning by reviewing the audio, video, or chat recordings after the session.

According to Irati de Nicolás Saiz Ariane Sande Piñeiro (2022), the instructor can simply set apart a certain amount of time per week simply to converse in the Foreign Language classroom. The instructor can decide whether an “authentic” conversation should take place, whether he or she wants a structured conversation, or whether students can benefit from a combination of the two. Conversation time can also be the perfect opportunity to discuss current events or previously read articles, short stories, movies, etc. depending on the level of the students. Some of our students may indeed be tempted to run away from conversation time and not come to class on the day that they know that oral interaction will be taking center stage. Thus, it is important to inform our students about the importance of acquiring communicative skills in the L2/FL and that the online class is the only space that they may currently have to do so. Another strategy, a stricter one, would be to make conversation time obligatory and an important percentage of the final grade. Radio shows or podcasts can also be a fantastic opportunity for your students to practice speaking in the L2/FL language. Students can be asked to create a podcast or a radio show in groups using the software that websites such as Podomatic offer. By creating a free account in Podomatic, each group can record their podcasts directly on the website and store 20 episodes for free (Podomatic, 2021). They will even have the chance to publish their podcast or radio show on iTunes, Spotify, or Google Play if they so desire. The instructor can decide how the different classroom podcasts must be shared with the rest of the class, and each group can come up with debate questions or even comprehension questions for the rest of the groups. Virtual exchanges with partner schools or partner universities can also be very beneficial. In this case, the instructor must partner up with a colleague who is interested in their students speaking Spanish as a Foreign language regularly with our students in exchange for English, the native language of our students. The partner instructors can design tasks for students to complete together, decide how much time they will speak Spanish and how

much time they will devote to English, when and how they must meet,

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how big the groups should be and if groups should always have the same members, etc. At the end of the exchange, which we recommend should last at least a few weeks, the different groups can present a small project or give a presentation through a video-conferencing platform.

A good example of how to put a virtual exchange into practice is Vinagre, Wigham & Giralt (2020). The authors carried out an Erasmus+ Virtual Exchange between three universities in Spain, France, and Ireland over six weeks. Vinagre et al. (2020) state that they received a very encouraging and positive response from the students who participated and that, overall, students reported an increase in self-confidence and self-reliance when communicating in the FL.

The “share screen” function inside Zoom means that instructors can use any ICT tool, website, or software on their computer and easily and automatically share it with their students. As Kohnke & Moorhouse (2022), Moorhouse & Kohnke (2020), and Kohnke (2021) argue, this very act facilitates active learning and interaction. The instructor can also use the poll function inside Zoom and provide students with a situation. Then, the instructor can ask students what they would do in that situation by showing them a poll with three options to choose from. Students then choose their answer and see other students’ responses as well. Finally, everyone’s choices are open for discussion. An activity of this kind means that students are engaged and that oral interaction is promoted. In our experience, this kind of activity has proven to be very effective and has increased students’ engagement and interaction. Hence, González-Lloret (2020), stated that it needs to consider the technological contexts of the students and teachers, as most of these activities require a stable and strong Internet connection.

According to the author, potential difficulties “can be solved by conducting a needs analysis to find out the participants’ technical capabilities, digital literacies, and institutional support”. González-Lloret (2020), further argues that, if need be, “we need to give students (and/or teachers) extra support and training so that technology is not the reason they fall behind. As educators, we should do everything in our power to narrow the digital divide and make online learning accessible and equitable.” Moreover, we must bear in mind that, as Jiang (2020), in González-Lloret, (2020) argue, video-conferencing platforms such as Zoom, although they facilitate our work (and study), require more focus

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and energy than a face-to-face conversation because we cannot read the body language as easily as in face-to-face, the different rhythm of pauses and conversation feel unnatural, and we are aware that we are being watched on camera. Thus, González-Lloret (2020) proposes that, if possible, "a combination of synchronous and asynchronous work may be key to finding balance and keep learners cognitively engaged in the task.

RELATED STUDIES

Foreign

Pronunciation is essential for effective communication since improper pronunciation almost always results in the recipient misinterpreting the message. Pronunciation of letter sounds in words, as well as syllable emphasis on parts of words, frequently drastically changes the meaning and context of the words, irreversibly changing the meaning of the statement being transmitted. Having incorrect pronunciation causes learners not to be understood, even if their grammar is perfect. The speech sounds way can have a big impact on whether or not to understand what they are saying and their initial impression. The tricky thing about pronunciation is that it is not just a question of acquiring knowledge, it is a physical skill that the learners need to practice regularly. So they should know the pronunciation (Kobilova, N. R. 2022).

According to Rehman, I., et. al. (2022), over 300 million people use Arabic as their first language across hundreds of miles in approximately 25 countries. Millions more speak it as a second language. Modern Standard Arabic, based on Classical Arabic, is used as the written and formal spoken standard in Arabic, alongside many varieties of spoken Arabic that differ from the written standard in various ways.

The Arabic language is one of the oldest and is distinguished by its originality and flexibility. Classical Arabic is the Quranic language, while Modern Standard Arabic is a modified variant that is today utilized in everyday speech. CA's pronunciation rules are very well-defined to retain the exact meaning of the words and serve as basic building blocks to assist both natives and non-natives in learning the Arabic language. The articulation points of the alphabet, peculiarities of the alphabet, and considerable vocal practice are the requirements to consider for perfect pronunciation. (Ziafat, N. et. al. 2021).

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Arabic is a developing and changing language. In science, technology, and culture, language always follows modernity. Arabic language or a foreign language has different characteristics and language structures from one another. Foreign language vocabulary can be used in both verbal and written communication. Speeches, news broadcasts, and sermons are examples of oral communication (Lubis, M. H., & Damanik, R. P. A., 2023). The Arabic learning process is aimed to improve language skills well also shifts to online-based learning.

According to the study of Wargadinata, W., et. al., (2020), COVID-19 emphasizes the importance of Arabic learning in emergencies. The learning process that takes place in the classroom is transformed into online learning, which has an impact on all activities that take place at home. On that premise, a study into the process of Arabic learning and the media employed in the COVID-19 emergency at UIN Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, which is one of the universities practicing online learning during this epidemic, is required. In practice, studying Arabic has an important component that is emphasized, namely, the improvement of language skills that should not be stopped. The pandemic situation then aided in shifting the process of learning Arabic to the usage of online media to achieve active participation of students in learning. Active language learning is the initial step for Arabic learners. So, under whatever conditions, language acquisition must continue, and language skills must be achieved to the greatest extent feasible. The process of collaborative active learning encounters becomes more directed, and the formation of a speaking environment is possible even in the context of online networks. The language environment is vital since it will considerably aid foreign speakers in learning or developing their language skills (Maburoh, 2017).

According to Krapchatova, Y., & Holovko, O. (2018), active learning activities aim to provide students with numerous opportunities to use language. As a result, individuals have a better chance of achieving fluency or communicative competence. This active collaborative interaction approach does result in an intensive program that is run in a committed manner by Arabic learners; learning must also be structured without being confined by time and geography, even when using online networks. A learner who is actively engaged in learning will be trained continuously and repeatedly in the language training process.

According to Li, V. (2017), Some skills can be improved through online language learning, including a) learners still receive guidance and supervision from the teacher; b) knowledge of language skills formed through the construction of language meaning; c) communication

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and integration of each

language skills, including listening, speaking, reading, and writing, so that there is integrated and holistic learning, and d) some language games can also improve students' critical thinking process. Language skills can be maximized and integrated through technology (Picciano, 2017).

With the arrival of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, it appears that the educational world will be influenced by the Information Age, in which the way humans learn will be digitized as well. Though the transition has been gradual, the recent outbreak of the Coronavirus, or COVID-19, has ultimately resulted in a major shift toward online classes, creating an urgent need for in-depth research on effective ways to conduct and offer online education to the public (Islam, M., Kim, D. A., & Kwon, M. 2020).

According to Lowenthal, P. et. al (2020), many faculty members, especially teacher educators, have chosen to convert their courses to live synchronous web meetings using web conferencing software such as Zoom. Zoom is a technology business based in the United States that offers video telephony and online chat services via a P2P (Peers-to-Peer) software platform. Zoom is now widely used around the world for telecommuting, distance learning, and teleconferencing (Islam, M., Kim, D. A., & Kwon, M. 2020).

According to Islam, M., Kim, D. A., & Kwon, M. (2020), the study has shown that pre-recorded video lectures are preferred to live Zoom lectures due to their flexibility, convenience, and educational effectiveness. Thus, it is clearly explained that students prefer pre-recorded video lectures over live Zoom lectures, as students can go through the video lectures as many times as they want, which gives independence in terms of time and space.

Local

The Holy Qur'an was revealed in Arabic. Allah (S. W. T) says: "Indeed We have made it an Arabic Qur'an that perchance you will comprehend." [Al-Qur'an 43:3] The above-quoted verse in the Holy Qur'an shows that the Arabic language is not merely a language of the Arabs but a language of all that must be learned to understand Islam. (Solaiman 2017). According to Ibrahim Al-Huri (2015), the Arabic language is one of the world's leading languages with more than 300 million native speakers in 22 Arab countries, where Arabic is the official language. According to .M. H. A., & Lulu, R. A. (2021), languages are not stagnant and are a part of the everchanging intercultural communication.

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Language is an applied art that makes human communication and interaction possible. It is a tool for learning other languages, philosophy, culture, arts, science, religion, and ideas. It is also a useful tool to access power and express feelings. It is flexible and adaptable as indicated in this study.

Synthesis

In conclusion, languages are not stagnant and are a part of the everchanging intercultural communication. Language is an applied art that makes human communication and interaction possible. It is a tool for learning other languages, philosophy, culture, arts, science, religion, and ideas. It is also a useful tool to access power and express feelings. It is flexible and adaptable (M. H. A., & Lulu, R. A., 2021).

Pronunciation is an important factor in learning a language. According to Yulduz (2021), good pronunciation means being understood. However, pronunciation receives less attention than the other subjects in language learning. Pronunciation is important for several reasons, particularly when speaking Arabic. The Holy Qur'an was revealed in Arabic. Thus, pronunciation is required especially for Muslims because they practice it in their prayers. The capacity to read the Qur'an has an impact on students' ability to read Arabic texts, according to both students and teachers who teach Arabic. The pronunciation of Arabic texts is greatly influenced by one's ability to read the Qur'an. Because the Qur'an is essentially an Arabic language. Furthermore, reading Arabic literature requires continuous pronunciation practice so that students may speak Arabic texts correctly and minimize errors in pronunciation (Nabilah et al., 2020). As there is an increase in learners of the Arabic language around the globe there is also an increase in interest as well as the shift to more online and blended environments shapes the future of education (Weber & Hamlaoui, 2018).

Online learning has included numerous and overlapping terms such as e-learning, blended learning, online education, online courses, etc (Singh, V., & Thurman, A., 2019). Globally, online learning has grown to be a significant part of education, including in the Philippines. Since the pandemic hit, educators and learners have been forced to integrate technology into the process of teaching and learning. In this era, schooling cannot be completed without the use of technology. As a

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result, research should be conducted and the educational curriculum should be revised.

One of the online platforms that is commonly used is Zoom technology. The use of Zoom technology enhances positive learning outcomes for diverse groups of students as well as encouraging higher education in remote areas while potentially reducing workloads for teachers. (N. Guzacheva, 2020). To adapt to the new normal, educational institutions must thoroughly redesign their services. Schools should create digital learning techniques and offer digital learning settings, resources, and support systems to create an effective online learning experience. Therefore, this study aims the effect of Zoom technology on the learning process of Arabic language students in their pronunciation.

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RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To answer the research questions of the study, an appropriate methodology needed to be chosen and decisions made about how the research would be undertaken. In this chapter, it will detail the selection of participants and sampling, procedures in data collection, and data analysis.

Research Design

The research design directly relates to the study questions or topic, the data to be collected, and the methodology to be used. It also depends on the ontological and epistemological orientation of the researcher. This means considering who the participants will be, how they will be selected, and how the data will be collected (data-gathering techniques). The research design also involves how the data are to be 'written up' and shared with participants, as well as how are to be analyzed, including measures of reliability, validity, and generalizability. (Grieshaber, S. 2020).

Concerning this, this research utilized a quasi-experimental research design. It aimed to determine the cause-and-effect relationship between independent and dependent variables in a target population and dependent variables in a target population without random assignment (Gopalan, M. et al., 2020).

The quasi-experimental design identifies a comparison group that is as similar as possible to the treatment group in terms of baseline (pre-intervention) characteristics. The main objective of this design was to answer the causality between the interdependent and dependent variables of this study. The variables of the study comprised Zoom technology (independent) and results of the post-test scores and feedback of the students (dependent). Research methods are the tools and techniques for doing research. Research is a term used liberally for any kind of investigation that is intended to uncover interesting or new facts and also a range of tools that are used for different types of inquiry (Walliman, N. 2021).The researcher will use a mixed-method design.

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According to Mixed Methods Utilisation in Innovation Management Research: A Systematic Literature Review and Meta-Summary (2020), mixed method design is the combined use of quantitative and qualitative methods in the same study. When viewed historically, the mixed methods approach can be seen as a methodology that was created at the end of the 1980s and the beginning of the 1990s. Its current iteration is a result of the work of researchers in several scientific fields, including sociology, education, management, and health sciences (Creswell and Creswell 2018). In a mixed-method approach, whereby researchers collect and analyze both quantitative and qualitative data within the same study (Allison and Joanna 2017). A purposeful mixing of methods is required in the data collecting, data analysis, and interpretation phases of mixed methods research. The key word here is "mixed," as linking or integrating data at the right point in the research process is a crucial component of the mixed methods approach.

According to Allison and Joanna (2017), purposeful data integration enables researchers to seek a more comprehensive view of their research landscape by looking at phenomena from various angles and through diverse research lenses.

This study aims to identify the significant post-test gain and the difference between the control and experimental group in Arabic language pronunciation skills by the quantitative data and determine the students' feedback on the use of Zoom in teaching Arabic pronunciation and the features of using Zoom technology as a learning platform that influenced the performance of students by qualitative data. Therefore, the mixed-method design is the appropriate design for the study.

As part of the mixed-method design, quantitative work is expressed in numbers and in statistical models (John Gerring, 2017) on which this study involved oral pronunciation tests to analyze the data. A quantitative method was followed to give a more objective justification for the results of hypothesis testing (Pourhosein et. Al, 2019).

The researcher will employ a quasi-experimental method in which it will attempt the cause-and-effect of Zoom technology among Arabic language learners in their pronunciation skills.

On the other hand, qualitative research is multimethod in focus,

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involving an interpretative, naturalistic approach to its subject matter. This means that qualitative researchers study things in their natural settings, attempting to make sense of or interpret, phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them (Patrik Aspers, 2019). In the qualitative study, the researcher will be they were interviewing Beginner students in Arabic language pronunciation to determine the students' feedback on the use of Zoom in teaching Arabic pronunciation and the features of using Zoom technology as a learning platform that influenced the performance of students.

Context and Participants

The sample is a portion of a population or universe. However, by population, many often consider people only. Population does not necessarily mean several people. It can also refer to the total quantity of the things or cases that are the subject of our research (Etikan, let. Al, 2016).

The fifty participants are Filipinos ages 18 years old to 64 years old who are Arabic Language students at the beginner's level and were selected from Arabic pronunciation classes at Dar Ash-shifaa Qur'aan school through probability sampling in simple random sampling method.

According to Huma Parveen and Nayeem Showkat (2017), sampling is the method of selecting a representative subset of the population called a sample. It's the sampling method that determines the generalizability of the research findings. In simple words, the process of choosing a sample of the population to study is called sampling. One of the probability sampling is simple random sampling which is a completely random method of selecting a sample in which each element and each combination of elements in the population have an equal probability of being selected as a part of the sample. (Huma Parveen and Nayeem Showkat, 2017). All of the students are Filipinos and Arabic Language is a foreign language to them.

Dar Ash-shifaa' Qur'aan school shifted to online distance learning due to the sudden catastrophe of COVID-19 and since then, the school has been exploring ways of the best practices in learning Arabic language pronunciation online. Thus, the researcher chooses to conduct the study in the said school.

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To gather qualitative data, twenty-five (25) available Beginner' students in Arabic language will be interviewed since they implement Zoom technology in learning Arabic language pronunciation. They are determined through purposive sampling. According to Chittaranjan Andrade (2021), a purposive sample is one whose characteristics are defined for a purpose that is relevant to the study.

Research Instrument

In this study, pre-tests and post-test were used and were self-made. The pre-test and post-test are used to measure the change in the student pronunciation skills throughout this study Pourhosein et. Al (2019). The test is an oral-based test composed of 29 Arabic letters and 3 sentences from the book called *Al-Qaai'dah An-Nooraniyyah*. The *Al-Qaai'dah An-Nooraniyyah* book is an essential and for the most part valued instructive asset for individuals of any age who need to obtain the key ideas of Arabic composition, elocution, and Quranic recitation. This book is a means of acquiring the skills of hearing, pronunciation, reading, and writing. For those who want to learn the Arabic language, the benefits of learning this book for adults are: learning the skill of correct, eloquent pronunciation and correct reading of letters, words, and sentences of the Arabic language. Hence, this is for the Arabic speakers, non-Arabic speakers, and the illiterate. In addition, it straightens the tongue and creates a qualitative shift in reading among adult learners (Furqancenter). The book can be bought online as a soft copy with audio that is designed specifically for the book. Moreover, it also has a software program which is also available in the Apple Store and Play Store. The book was used as a material by the students. Therefore, the book is suitable for this study.

Pronunciation Assessment Test

The pronunciation test is an oral test to be used as a pre-test and post-test.

The researcher will ask the beginner students to read aloud the 29 Arabic letters and the 3 sentences. Each letter is equivalent to one point and each sentence is equivalent to two points. Therefore, the overall points are 35 points. According to Ho Dang Tuong Nguyen (2018), a commonly used way of pronunciation assessment is reading aloud. The reading-

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cloud testing provides good control and enables to test of almost all aspects of pronunciation.

The reliability test is used for quantitative data. A reliability test, in the context of research and assessment, is a statistical method used to evaluate the consistency, stability, and dependability of a measurement tool, such as a test, questionnaire, or assessment. It assesses the extent to which the tool yields consistent and reproducible results when administered to the same group of individuals or under similar conditions. In this specific study, the Pronunciation Assessment Tool underwent a reliability test (Cronbach's Alpha was used) to determine how consistently it measures pronunciation skills.

The instrument for gathering quantitative data for this research will be validated by 3 experts in the field of Education who already have a doctor's degree in educational management and 1 expert who already has a doctor's degree in the Arabic Language.

For the qualitative instrument, this research used an open-ended questionnaire for semi-structured interviews of students of beginners in Arabic Language. The questions to ask are the demographic profile of the students, their

feedback on using Zoom technology, learning experience between non-zoom technology and Zoom technology, challenges/problems they encounter in using Zoom, features of Zoom technology that improve their pronunciation skills, and suggestions on using Zoom technology in Arabic language teaching.

The instrument for gathering qualitative data for this research will be validated by 3 experts in the field of Education who already have a doctorate in educational management and 1 expert who already has a doctorate in the Arabic Language.

Procedure

This research aims to determine the effect of Zoom technology among Arabic language students on their pronunciation skills. The researcher strictly followed the standard operating system for this study from pre-gathering data and post-gathering data.

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Pre-gathering of Data

The researcher obtained permission to collect data from the school head, teachers' permission to use some time out of their class to administer the test, and student consent to participate in the oral pretest and posttest that will be given by the researcher in Arabic Language for Beginners' students. The consent must be gathered and signed to authorize the researcher to conduct the data gathering for students before administering the test and interview.

For interviewing, the researcher will interview beginner students in the Arabic language who implemented Zoom technology in their learning of Arabic pronunciation. The interview will be held through the Zoom platform.

Open-ended questions will be asked to students to determine the effect of Zoom technology on their Arabic language pronunciation skills. The process of interviewing will last for one week depending on the availability of the students.

Post Gathering Data

In quantitative analysis, the pretest and posttest of the students were checked and the gain scores of the test were recorded and analyzed statistically. While in qualitative analysis, the answers from the interview were compiled and analyzed thematically.

Data Analysis

Quantitative analysis

In this study, the quantitative data gathered from the oral pretest and posttest of the Beginner students in the Arabic language was computed using various statistical tools. A software of SPSS Version 20 was used to compute the statistics. Pretest and posttest results were accumulated, and scores were recorded in a class record. It contained scores of learners for 32-item oral pretest and posttest but the 3 sentences are equivalent to two points each therefore the total score is 35 points. The results of the pretest-posttest of the Control Group and Experimental Group were used to determine the effect of Zoom technology on Arabic language students on their pronunciation skills.

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Paired t-test

The paired t-test is one type of inferential statistics. In paired sample t-test is a tool to measure the hypothesis in which the data used are not independent (pairs) (lin, J. et. al, 2022). and also referred to as a dependent t-test or a matched pairs t-test, is a statistical hypothesis test used to determine whether a significant difference exists between the means of two related groups. It is specifically designed for situations where you have paired or matched observations, meaning that each data point in one group is somehow linked or matched with a data point in the other group. The fundamental concept is to compare the differences between the paired data points to evaluate whether a statistically significant difference exists. In this study, a paired t-test is employed to assess whether there is a significant difference in pronunciation test scores before and after using non-Zoom technology in the control group, providing a statistical evaluation of the platform's effectiveness.

Gain Scores

However, the gain scores of the test scores are usually done to assess the effects of one treatment over time and compare the results of two groups. To compute the gain score, the following formula is used $\text{Gain Score} = \text{Posttest} - \text{Pre-test}$

In this study, the gain score was used to compare the scores of the control and treatment groups on the pretest and posttest. After the computation of the gain score of the two groups, it was subjected to statistics.

Wilcoxon signed-rank test:

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test is a non-parametric statistical test used to assess whether there is a significant difference between paired or related observations. It's used when the data doesn't meet the assumptions of a paired t-test. In this study, as the data in the experimental group is not normally distributed, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to determine if there was a statistically significant change in the pronunciation test scores of the experimental group before and after their use of the Zoom-based platform. This test assesses the platform's effectiveness in improving pronunciation skills.

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Mann-Whitney U test:

The Mann-Whitney U test, also known as the Wilcoxon rank-sum test, is a non-parametric statistical test used to compare two independent groups and determine if a significant difference exists between them. It assesses whether one group tends to have larger values than the other. In this study, the Mann-Whitney U test was employed to assess whether a significant difference exists in pronunciation test scores between the control group and the experimental group following the intervention. This choice was made because the data in the experimental group did not follow a normal distribution. The test's purpose is establish whether one group exhibited a statistically significant improvement in pronunciation skills compared to the other. It is applied when the assumptions of a parametric test, such as an independent t-test, are not met, particularly when dealing with non-normally distributed data or ordinal data.

Normality Test:

A normality test is a statistical procedure used to assess whether a dataset follows a normal distribution, also known as a Gaussian distribution. The normal distribution is a specific type of probability distribution with a bell-shaped curve, characterized by its mean and standard deviation. Many statistical methods and tests assume that data is normally distributed, so it's essential to check if this assumption holds. In this study, the Shapiro-Wilk test is a specific normality test. It is used to determine whether the differences in means between the Control Group and the Experimental Group follow a normal distribution.

Qualitative Analysis

In this study, the qualitative phase, the thematic content analysis of the data will be used by the researcher. According to Wen and Katina (2020), thematic analysis (TA) is a commonly used qualitative data analysis approach. It is a qualitative method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns within a data corpus (Scharp and Sanders, 2018). Thematic analysis is a suitable method of analysis for seeking to understand experiences, thoughts, or behaviors across a data set

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(Michelle and Lara, 2020). In thematic analysis, the data gathered was grouped according to the themes which are the students' feedback on the use of Zoom in teaching Arabic pronunciation and the features of using Zoom technology as a learning platform that influenced the performance of students. It begins with weeding out biases and forming overarching impressions of the data. The data from the interview was used by the researcher to find common patterns across the data set.

Instrument Validation Procedure

This study was conducted to determine the effect of Zoom technology in Arabic language classrooms on students' pronunciation skills.

The pretest and posttest that the researcher made for gathering quantitative data needed validation from experts. To accomplish the study, the four validators contributed their knowledge of educational management and the Arabic language. There was one expert with a doctoral degree in Arabic language, a lecturer from the Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan. The other one is a doctor's degree in Education majoring in educational management currently teaching at Mindanao State University – Main Campus as an associate professor V. The other validator is currently an Associate professor at San Beda University, Manila with a doctorate in Education. The last validator is a doctorate in Education majoring in educational management at the National University, Manila.

The four validators also validated the instrument for qualitative data. The instrument is the interview questions of the study to identify the students' feedback on the use of Zoom technology in teaching Arabic pronunciation and the features of using Zoom technology as a learning platform that influenced the performance of students. Attached to the validation instrument is the validation form which gives a guide to the experts in validating the instruments. The experts ticked the appropriate boxes- accept reject or need revision in the validation form. A column on "remarks" and a space for comments and suggestions were added to allow experts to write their additional inputs in the instrument. A validator's agreement form is also used to determine whether they approved the instrument even without the review of the final copy with revisions. Several days after the instruments were checked and validated, the researcher made the necessary corrections.

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Ethical Considerations

Every research study must prioritize the protection of human participants by adhering to the relevant ethical guidelines (Arifin, S. R. M., 2018). Thus, the researcher observed ethical considerations in the study. The researcher sent a letter of permission to conduct the study to the school head and students. The participants were informed of the purpose, procedures, and duration of the study. Additionally, it was made clear to them that they had the option to ask questions, decline from responding to the questions, or withdraw from participating in the study. The collection of the data would be handled professionally and confidentially, it was further conveyed as an assurance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The use of Zoom technology as a learning platform in the process of learning and teaching pronunciation is very significant, especially in developing students' Arabic language pronunciation skills and for them to be more knowledgeable and understandable in their speaking when they are in real-life situations. This study aimed to determine the effect of Zoom

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technology in the Arabic language classroom on students' pronunciation skills. The participants in the qualitative research are the experimental group of Beginners' level from Dar Ashifa'a Qur'an School with the intervention of Zoom Technology.

RQ 1. Students' feedback on the use of Zoom technology in teaching Arabic pronunciation

To determine the effect of Zoom technology in the Arabic language classroom on students' pronunciation skills, the researcher conducted qualitative research through an interview with twenty-five beginner students learning Arabic language pronunciation through Zoom technology and analyzed the gathered data through thematic analysis.

Based on the interview, the student's feedback on the use of Zoom technology is the difference between their learning on using Zoom and non-zoom technology, the challenges they encountered while using Zoom, and their suggestion to improve the pronunciation skills in teaching the Arabic language

through Zoom technology. Therefore, we will break it down into categories to understand the student feedback.

- A. What is the difference between your learning on using Zoom Technology and Non-Zoom Technology?

Delivery format of learning

Zoom is a collaborative, cloud-based videoconferencing service offering features including online meetings, group messaging services, and secure recording of sessions (Archibald, M. M., et. al 2019). As the student stated, "The difference is the physical component. In a face-to-face classroom, the student is physically present while in Zoom the student is virtually present. In that case, the traditional mode of learning face-to-face is held in the same location whereas the Zoom technology takes place online." With this, the difference is that Zoom Technology is an online mode of delivery of teaching and learning whereas the face-to-face class is a physical mode.

Zoom Technology learning is a mode of learning that takes place online, typically through video conferencing platforms. Students and instructors interact through video and audio, often in real-time, but from different locations. Hence, interactions occur through digital tools, such as chat, video, and audio. These interactions may lack the richness of face-

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to-face communication but can still be engaging. In Face-to-Face Learning, a traditional mode of learning, students and instructors are physically present in the same location, such as a classroom or a campus. Interactions occur in person.

Location of the participants

Zoom Technology allows users to interact with people who are geographically separated in real-time via a computer, tablet, or mobile device (Archibald, M. M., et. al 2019). Students can participate from anywhere with internet access. "In Zoom technology, I've met and interacted with other participants from different places and learned from my teacher even though we are far away unlike in face-to-face classes." the student responded. Zoom offers flexibility for learners who may not be able to attend physical classes. In a face-to-face class, students need to be present at the physical location where the class or educational institution is located. According to Gowda, R., & Ayush, G. K. (2020), Zoom technology enables learning from anywhere and anytime. The students can access the recorded lectures at their convenience and the faculties can also schedule live classes at their convenience.

Accessibility

Zoom Technology learning provides access to a wide range of digital resources, but access to physical facilities and equipment may be limited. According to HyeJeong Kim (2020), Zoom technology can provide easier access to course resources. Whereas, physical learning, offers immediate access to physical resources like libraries, labs, and in-person support services. Student responded, "Zoom technology is accessible and convenient for students who are busy and don't have time to go to school, unlike physical learning." Because of the advancement of Zoom technology, the period of learners convening physically

in classrooms has mostly vanished. Zoom technology and how to use it are generally known to modern learners who are also digital natives. At this moment, it is vital to assess the effectiveness of remote video classes delivered via Zoom (HyeJeong Kim, 2020).

The student also mentioned that "Compared to other online platforms, Zoom technology is more formal in learning and teaching. Hence, it specializes in conducting classes and meetings." In the study "Using Zoom Videoconferencing for Qualitative Data Collection:

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Perceptions and Experiences of Researchers by Archibald, M. M., et. al (2019), there are typical issues associated with using Skype reported in previous studies include dropped calls and pauses, poor audio or video quality, and the inability to read nonverbal cues as a result of inconsistent and delayed connectivity unlike in Zoom technology. "Zoom technology has clear and better video and audio while the other online tool has blurred video and the audio is not clear causing a hindrance to the class." said the student. The other student also stated, "Zoom technology is a user-friendly tool to learn and practice Arabic language pronunciation compared with other programs" and the other student mentioned, "Compared to other online platforms, Zoom technology is more formal in learning and teaching. Hence, it specializes in conducting classes and meetings." And also said, "The Zoom technology gives justice in pronouncing the sound of every letter as it has a clear audio feature." Therefore, Zoom technology is accessible compared to other online programs.

Costs and Commute

Through Zoom Technology, the student can save on commuting costs and time, but may still have tuition fees unlike in face-to-face class, which requires commuting and may have additional costs for housing, transportation, and campus-related expenses. According to HyeJeong Kim (2020), Students (and faculty) can independently access the event or course at a time and location of their choosing via the affordances of technology. As the student responded, "In Zoom technology you can multi-task. At the same time, you can be attentive in class while doing other things." In addition, physical learning formats capitalize on simultaneous student and faculty interactions and require students and faculty to be in the same place at the same time (Kay, D., & Pasarica, M., 2019). Therefore, students can save money and time which makes learning easy.

In conclusion, according to the student experience, the difference between using Zoom and non-zoom technology is that there is a highly positive impact of Zoom technology as an educational tool in learning the Arabic language and developing pronunciation skills. This has also been discovered in the study of Shabani et al. (2022), that Zoom has become popular due to the various advantages users have experienced. The comfort of using Zoom and the success in delivering learning materials by the host and receiving them from the participants has driven many users to opt for Zoom technology.

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Moreover, compared to other online platforms, the teachers suggested that Zoom is better suited to distance learning because the connection is reliable, the quality of video and audio is excellent, and more available tools for delivering the target lesson for the students (R Nurieva, Guzel, and Leila M Garaeva., 2020). As the student responded, "There is no excuse for not developing your Arabic pronunciation skills for learning through Zoom technology is almost the same as face-to-face classes because of its functions and features."

B. What are the challenges you experience while using Zoom Technology in your learning of Arabic pronunciation?

However, despite its numerous advantages, Zoom technology has some challenges, though over time many of these challenges have been addressed.

Internet network and connectivity issue

Common problem in an online setting is connectivity problems. Users may experience issues with internet connectivity, leading to disruptions in audio and video. According to Gowda, R., & Ayush, G. K. (2020), Internet network and connectivity issues is a major disadvantage of online teaching especially for students living in remote areas of the country. As the student affirmed, " The Zoom technology requires a strong internet connection to be in the class and to be fully engaged in the activities. "the other support statement, " In Zoom technology, I have difficulty staying in class due to the unstable internet connection and power interruption." And, "The sound and video are delayed in Zoom

technology due to poor internet connection. And for that, I can't understand my classmates and teacher."

Unavailability of specific device or gadget

By using Zoom technology, the device must be compatible with the program. As Gowda, R., & Ayush, G. K. (2020) stated, about 28% of students identified that the availability of required electronic devices for conducting classes in the hands of students coming from rural areas and from poor families is another

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drawback and a major hurdle in implementing online teaching. This is supported by the response of the student, "You need to have a good gadget or device that meets the specifications of Zoom technology. Or else you can't access Zoom."

According to the students who participated in the interview, students must have a strong internet connection so that they can communicate comfortably. Also, the participants or users need to have devices with good specifications.

Almost all the students' challenges faced in using Zoom technology is the poor internet connection and the others must have a suitable device for the said technology. The weak internet connection has also been mentioned in the study Investigating The Zoom Application as A Video Conferencing Platform in The Online Learning Process Based on Teacher's Perception by Dantes, Gede Rasben, et al (2022), the first disadvantage when using Zoom as a teaching and learning medium is an unstable internet connection. Hence, an internet connection is essential in the Zoom platform's teaching and learning process.

However, other than that, the students appreciated using Zoom technology as an educational platform for learning Arabic language pronunciation. Therefore, students' suggestions are asked on how to improve their Arabic pronunciation skills using Zoom technology in teaching.

C. What do you think the use of Zoom technology helps you in improving your pronunciation skills in the Arabic language?

More one-on-one learning sessions with teacher or peer

Virtual communication may lack the richness of face-to-face interaction, making it challenging to pick up on subtle non-verbal cues. For this reason, the student may ask for more time to practice their pronunciation skill. According to Gowda, R., & Ayush, G. K. (2020), the online mode of teaching suffers from a lack of face-to-face interaction between the faculties and the students. There is a missing element of personal touch in the case of online modes of teaching and learning, especially in the case of presentations and demonstrations. The student mentioned, "I am satisfied with the overall function of Zoom technology but I would like to suggest having more time in the class to practice my pronunciation skills with my teacher and peers." And also another student stated, "If there is a possibility, we can meet outside class hours to play a

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game about Arabic language pronunciation through Zoom technology like a contest of who would identify the letter and pronounce it correctly.”

Visual presentation or demonstration

Certain subjects or activities that require hands-on experience may be challenging to teach or learn through virtual platforms. The online method of instruction suffers from a lack of face-to-face interaction between faculty and students. In the case of online teaching and learning, there is a lack of a personal touch, particularly in the case of presentations and demonstrations (Gowda, R., & Ayush, G. K., 2020). With this, the student suggested, “My suggestion is to show a video clip or image in Zoom technology of what part of the mouth we need to use to pronounce every Arabic letter.”

Based on the interview, the students who participated in the study suggested that to extend the class timing to develop their pronunciation skills and letting the teacher show a video clip of every Arabic letter articulation point. And to include game activities outside class hours.

All in all, most of the students had no suggestions as they were content and satisfied with what they expected in learning the Arabic language and developing their pronunciation skills through Zoom technology. According to Hind and Hassan (2021), learners can participate in a variety of different educational activities within the Zoom environment and students and educators can also meet individually to discuss the student's work. Therefore, the overall students' feedback is that there is a highly positive effect on the use of Zoom technology in teaching Arabic pronunciation.

RQ 2. Significant posttest gain in the Arabic pronunciation skills of students after being exposed to a Zoom-based platform

Before the intervention, the Control Group and Experimental Group were given a Pre-test through the Pronunciation Assessment tool focused on the basic Arabic language letters and three sentences from the book called *Al-Qaai'dah An- Nooraniyyah*. The control group was taught in Arabic language with the use of Non-Zoom technology as an intervention and the Experimental group was taught with the use of Zoom technology as an intervention of the group. The pronunciation assessment tool administered to the student was composed of twenty-nine Arabic letters and a sentences test. The Arabic letters are considered the basis of Arabic

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language pronunciation skills. (Ahmad and Soleh, 2019).

Table 1

Pronunciation Skills of Beginner Students based on their Post Gain

STATISTICAL TOOLS	CONTROL GROUP		EXPERIMENTAL GROUP	
	Pretest	Posttest	Pretest	Posttest
Mean	19.36	30.72	15.80	32.96
Standard Deviation	5.85	3.29	6.25	2.30
Mean Guide Score	11.36		17.16	
Test Value	9.32		-4.37	
p-value	0.00		0.00	

$a = \text{Posttest Score} - \text{Pretest Score}$

The result shown in Table 1, those who use Zoom Technology as a learning platform have a higher pronunciation score than those who did not. Control group had a mean of 30.72 and the Experimental group got 32.96 after being given a post-test. The mean gain score was greater

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for the Experimental group 17.16 compared to the control group 11.36.

The difference in the mean gain score of the two groups was attributed to the technology used as a learning platform in Arabic pronunciation. The experimental group was given intervention using Zoom technology. The intervention was started after checking the pre-test. The researcher reviews the lesson to improve and fill in the gaps in the students' pronunciation skills development.

According to the results of the Beginner students in the Experimental group 32.96 demonstrated more substantial improvements in pronunciation skills compared to those in the control group 30.72. This was made possible by using Zoom technology as a learning platform for Beginner students in Arabic pronunciation. As discovered by Kim, H.'s (2020) in his study, showed that real-time Zoom video lectures have a positive effect on learners' English reading achievement. Also in the study of Kohnke, L., & Moorhouse, B. L. (2022), when face-to-face teaching is not possible due to health emergencies or geographical distances between teachers and students, Zoom has enormous potential for second language acquisition, providing educators with a useful tool for formatively assessing learning, facilitating small group interactions, engaging learners, and extending learning beyond the 'traditional' classroom.

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Table 2

STATISTICAL TOOLS	CONTROL GROUP		EXPERIMENTAL GROUP	
	Pretest	Posttest	Pretest	Posttest
Mean	19.36	30.72	15.80	32.96
Standard Deviation	5.85	3.29	6.25	2.30
Mean Guide Score	11.36		17.16	
Test Value	9.32		-4.37	
p-value	0.00		0.00	

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Verbal Interpretation	Highly significant difference
Decision Rule	If the $p < 0.001$. It provides strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis, thus it has a highly significant difference.

Comparison of the Pretest and Post-test Gain Results of Control and Experimental Group

** $p < 0.05$; significant*

In table 2, the results reveal significant improvements in scores for both groups from the pretest to the posttest. Therefore, there is a significant difference. Additionally, the p-values for both groups were less than 0.05, confirming the statistical significance of the improvements. This suggests that the improvements were not due to chance but rather a result of the intervention. In conclusion, the intervention significantly enhanced pronunciation test scores in both groups, with the experimental group showing a potentially more substantial response, as supported by reduced variability and low p-values. In the study of Wu et al. (2017), an online learning environment may also help EFL students to improve oral language proficiency when they have the opportunity to record dialogue and participate in a flipped classroom whereby instruction is delivered online outside of class hours and class hours are used for practice. Thus, Zoom technology was simply used as a tool for the teacher to deliver the content that would have been covered in a face-to-face setting, with few opportunities to interact with students and check their understanding Cheung, A. (2023), Gowda, R., & Ayush, G. K. (2020), Guillén, G., Sawin, T., & Avineri, N. (2020).

RQ 3: Significant difference in the Arabic pronunciation skills between the control and experimental group

In Table 3, Comparison of the post-test results of the two groups shown in the next page it just shows that the mean difference, representing the gap in gain scores between the experimental and control groups, is 5.80, indicating that the experimental group improved by 5.80 points more on average. The low p-value (0.003) signifies that the mean gain scores between the two groups is statistically different. This implies that the used of the Zoom technology as a learning platform is better for developing students' pronunciation skills.

Compared to the used of non-zoom technology, students' hardly develop their pronunciation skills in the Arabic language. Since Zoom technology is accessible and easier to use as a learning platform it is

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better to use it to improve Arabic pronunciation for the students.

Table 3

Comparison of the Post-test Results of Control Group and Experimental Group

Descriptive Statistics	Mean	Std. Deviation
Control Group	11.36	6.10
Experimental Group	17.16	7.26
Mean Difference	5.90	
Test Value	-2.98	
p-value	0.003	

α = Experimental Group – Control Group

Table 3 displays summary statistics for gain scores, which denote the difference between posttest and pretest scores in the control and experimental groups. The experimental group had a higher mean gain score (17.16) compared to the control group (11.36), indicating more significant improvement. While the control group had a standard deviation of 6.10, the experimental group had a slightly higher standard deviation of 7.26, suggesting more variability in gain scores within the experimental group. In summary, these results highlight that, on average, the experimental group showed more substantial improvement in pronunciation skills compared to the control group. Despite slightly higher variability in gain scores within the experimental group, the mean difference and low p-value underscore the intervention's effectiveness in

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enhancing pronunciation skills in the experimental group. As discovered by Nuraziza, N., Oktaviani, L., & Sari, F. M. (2021), the implementation of Zoom supports online learning and most students thought implementation of e-learning should be improved continuously. Surprisingly, it gave significant changes toward the learning and teaching process. Also, Guillén, G., Sawin, T., & Avineri, N. (2020) in their study, as an immediate solution to remote language instruction needs, videoconferencing tools such as Zoom are commonly used. And the findings from the study of Singh, C. K. et. al. (2020), showed that the ESL teachers have resorted to Zoom as to engage the students in the learning process. Conducting lessons through Zoom technology provided teachers with more opportunities to use interactive apps Anisa Cheung; (2021).

Overall, educators have utilized a range of online synchronous meeting tools like Zoom technology to facilitate student learning. If remote classes must be prolonged, instructors must learn how to implement technological tools including Zoom and develop class activities and teaching strategies suitable for video lectures that can encourage learners' active participation.

RQ 4: The features of using Zoom technology as a learning platform that influenced the performance of Arabic language students.

To determine the effect of Zoom technology in the Arabic language classroom on students' pronunciation skills, the researcher conducted qualitative

research through an interview with twenty-five beginner students learning Arabic language pronunciation through Zoom technology and analyzed the gathered data through thematic analysis.

Based on the interview, the features of using Zoom technology as a learning platform that influenced the performance of Arabic language students are Video conferencing, Screen sharing, Reaction, Breakout Rooms, Chat Feature, Whiteboard, Raise Hand feature and Annotation feature.

The Features of Zoom technology as a Learning Platform that Influenced the Performance of Arabic Language Beginners' Students'

Video Conferencing

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Videoconferencing tools such as Zoom are being widely used as an immediate response to remote language teaching needs (Guillén, G., Sawin, T., & Avineri, N., 2020). As the student stated that, "Through the video conferencing feature, I can clearly see the teacher's and the other participants' faces with a clear voice, and likewise, they can hear and see me as well. And for that matter, the experience is almost the same as the face-to-face classes. We can promptly respond to each other and help each other improve our pronunciation skills." As this is also discovered by Nadezhda, G. (2020), in his study, Zoom is a cloud based service which offers Meetings and Webinars and provides content sharing and video conferencing capability. It helps, teachers bring their students together in a frictionless environment to get more done.

Screen sharing

Teachers and students can share their screens with other participants, making it easy to collaborate and present information. In the study of Moorhouse and Kohnke, (2020); Kohnke (2019), Zoom allows teachers and students to share browser screens synchronously so teachers can incorporate student response systems, such as Mentimeter and GoSoapBox, to leverage the interactive environment and facilitate active learning. As the student affirmed, "I can visualize the lesson through the Screen Sharing feature. The Arabic letters were presented clearly by the teacher, and I don't need to wear my glasses to view the lesson because of the Zoom-in option which I can enlarge my screen while the teacher is screen sharing."

Reaction

Zoom introduced a feature called "Reactions" that allows participants in a Zoom meeting to express themselves and provide non-verbal feedback. These reactions are similar to emoji or emoticons and can be used to convey sentiments and reactions during the meeting. As the student stated, "Through the reaction feature, I can interact and express my feelings with the teacher and other participants besides the video-conferencing." As mentioned by Kohnke, L., & Moorhouse, B. L. (2022), Zoom allows students to indicate through non-verbal icons when they have a question, show agreement or indicate if they want the teacher to speed up, slow down or take a break. These icons can provide useful information regarding students' attentiveness, excitement, agreement or

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confusion

with the language content being presented. Thus, Participants can click on these reaction icons located in the Zoom meeting controls to express their feelings or reactions in real-time. These reactions are displayed briefly on the video feed for all participants to see and can help to create a more interactive and engaging meeting experience.

Breakout Rooms

This feature allows hosts to split a large meeting into smaller, private groups for discussions or activities. In Arabic pronunciation class, student are partnered with each other and assigned in each breakout room. The learners practice and recited every lesson to help each other's pronunciation skills. According to Kohnke, L., & Moorhouse, B. L. (2022), teachers can provide opportunities for students to use language effectively, produce meaning-focused output, and engage in student-to-student contact by using Zoom's 'breakout room' function. Language acquisition requires meaning-focused output and student-to-student contact (Nation, 2007). Within a session, for example, students can be placed in small groups or couples to engage in spoken language practice, debates, and role-plays. This is also supported by a student, "Breakout room helps me significantly in improving my pronunciation skills. This feature enhances the peer evaluation activity or the one-on-one consultation with the instructor. You have privacy with no interruption while listening and reading the Arabic letters correctly.

Chat Feature

Zoom offers a text chat feature that allows participants to communicate via text during meetings. In the study of Spathis, P., & Dey, R. (2020), the in-meeting chat allows the participants to interact by sending instant messages during a meeting. Messages can be sent either to one or all participants. Participants can also send files other participants can choose to download from their chat panel. The host of the meeting can disable this feature or choose who the participants can chat with or to disable chat entirely. The host can select to have all chat messages saved in the meeting settings before the start or during the meeting. Private chat messages can help raise student willingness or motivation to engage, especially for those feeling under peer pressure, As the student stated, "In the Chatroom meeting, I can directly private message the teacher or any participant without anyone knowing. For example, after

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we evaluate our partner's pronunciation, we will report it to the teacher privately through the chat box during class."

Whiteboard

For collaborative drawing and visual explanations, Zoom has a built-in whiteboard feature. Videoconferencing softwares allow for screen sharing from a tablet connected wirelessly or via cable to the main device. Coupled to a digital pen, the tablet can be used as a digital whiteboard or to show and annotate presentation slides. This way, the main purpose of the computer is to run the videoconferencing software. Such setup can improve the monitoring of

participants' feedback (Spathis, P., & Dey, R. 2020). The student supported, "I can understand the lesson better because of the Whiteboard feature. The teacher explains and writes down the Arabic letters on the whiteboard which have closer sounds."

Raise Hand Feature

The "Raise Hand" reaction indicates that a participant wants to ask a question or make a comment. It's a way to virtually raise your hand to get the host's attention. As the student stated, "The Raise Hand feature helped organize the participants by order. For example, if we are ready to read to the teacher we will raise our hand virtually, and automatically Zoom will arrange the participants in order of who raises their hand first. This helps us to know who recites first and also, we prepare ourselves before reciting to the teacher." Nonverbal functions also allow the teacher to provide corrective feedback (Kohnke, L., & Moorhouse, B. L. 2022).

Annotation feature

Zoom provides an annotation feature that allows participants in a meeting to draw and mark up the shared screen or whiteboard. This can be useful for collaborative discussions, presentations, or educational purposes. As explained by Spathis, P., & Dey, R. (2020), screen annotation is the host and participants if enabled by the host can annotate the content shared on the screen. The annotation tools include text, draw (lines, arrows, and shapes), stamp (icons) like a check mark or a star),

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spotlight (presenter's mouse pointer is displayed within the area being shared to help point out parts of the screen). The host can save the screen with all annotations which will be captured as screenshot images. The student responded, "Through Screen sharing, the Annotation feature is used to emphasize the pronunciation errors I have. The teacher highlighted or marked my mistakes on the soft copy of the book using this feature. Thus, I can mark my book, record my mistakes, and review it after the class."

According to the interview of the students who participated, their performance in pronunciation skills is highly influenced by the features of Zoom technology as a learning platform. Singh and Thurman (2019) define online learning as "learning experienced through the internet/online computers in a synchronous classroom where students interact with instructors and other students and are not dependent on their physical location for participating in this online learning experience." And according to Shabani, Ramadhani Mashaka, et al (2022), Zoom technology that has become popular has its features embodied in this definition, and students will have no problem perceiving online education from this perspective.

Therefore, the features of Zoom technology as a learning platform has great influenced the performance on students' pronunciation skills of the Arabic language.

RQ 5. The instructional materials proposal

Technology is used in education in the twenty-first century and the majority of the students are computer literate. Since more people have access to technology, it is important to investigate interactive tools for Arabic language students so that they can learn the language in a more real-world setting. In this regard, the findings of this study are encouraging, and further work in this area will be useful. Therefore, the output of the study can contribute to the Arabic pronunciation course or any kind of language which is not only designed from an instructional design supported by a face-to-face approach but also an instructional design supported by an online approach that involves developing pronunciation skills which leads to greater student participation.

Instructional Design for An Online Arabic Pronunciation Class

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Instructional Design
Online Course

Course Description:

I. Course Description and Objective

This course is designed to introduce the students to the basic Arabic phonology of the Classical Arabic letters. It will provide a solid foundation, at the beginners' level, in the structure, pronunciation of Classical Arabic with a focus on Arabic letters in particular. As a conversation-based course the class will focus on the communicative skills of listening, speaking and developing the skills necessary to function in an Arabic-speaking environment. The students will learn to pronounce

orally the 29 Arabic letters. They will develop their listening comprehension skills and an awareness of differences in pronunciation. A variety of authentic audio and video as well as reading materials will be presented in this course. Students are encouraged to be creative with the language in and out of class. A core component of the class will be the memorization and recitation of different letters, vocabulary, and intonation patterns of Classical Arabic. Active participation in all class activities is of great importance to demonstrate progress in Classical Arabic, and to achieve a mastery level of Spoken Arabic.

II. Requirements and Policies:

1. Attendance, Punctuality, Make-Up policy:

Perfect attendance is required. If you must miss a class for some reason, it is your responsibility to contact the instructor or a classmate to find out what was covered and make up for the assignment. Otherwise, you will lose points. Attendance, preparation, and active class participation are very important. It is disruptive to the class to have students arriving late so please make your best effort to be on time. Students are expected to attend all classes. A student is responsible for work done, and for any announcements made, during his/her absence. The student has to video record his/her recitation of the missed assignment and then send it to his/her teacher before the next class starts and this must be checked carefully by the teacher.

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2. Preparation and Participation: Please be fully prepared for class. Learning a language is a process that requires the effort of the student more than anything

else. Preparing for class by listening to the audio of the lesson being studied, reading and practicing the lesson 3 times, doing homework, etc. This course revolves around an interactive class environment. Show that you are prepared by participating in pair work and group work and by responding to questions from the teacher and other students; making comments and giving your opinion. All students are expected to participate positively and constructively in all class activities.

3. Homework: Homework will be assigned by the instructor on a regular basis.

Homework will usually be listening to the audio of the assigned lesson and practicing it at least 3 times. The student will also be asked to practice in front of the mirror for the correct pronunciation of every letter. Homework evaluation is based on the effort and completion of the assignment and it will be tested in the next class.

4. Arabic in Class: The students are required to use Classical Arabic at all times in class. They will listen to their classmates and give them feedback on their comprehensibility.

5. Help with Arabic: The students feel free to contact the instructor if they need to work more on the language skills outside the classroom. The instructor is willing to help in overcoming any difficulties that the student might encounter.

III. Textbook and Supplementary Materials

1 Lesson, soft copy of the book, and Audio materials downloadable from the internet, and the hard copy of the book is attainable from the website.

- Qaida Al Nooraniya Youtube channel: <https://bit.ly/308bqaP>
- Nooraniya app on Appstore: <https://apple.co/364DXBP>
- Nooraniya app on Android: <https://bit.ly/331KxXO>
- Shop for the material: <https://furqanshop.com/>

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- Al-Qaai'dah An-Nooraniyyah book by Noor Muhammad Haqqani
- This course will use the Zoom application and is downloadable from the internet.

Syllabus Of Classes

Week One	Introduction and Requirements/Characteristics of Classical Arabic pronunciation
Week Two	Importance of the lip movements and the correct tune of the book
Week Three	The Heavy Letters and Light letters
Week Four	Practicing the almost sounds like letters into groups
Week Five	Spelling of the letters along with the Sun (الشمسية) letters and the Moon (القمرية) letters
Week Six	Exam

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CONCLUSION

In this study, the researcher determines the effects of Zoom technology in the Arabic language on students' pronunciation skills. Students were given intervention using Zoom technology and non-Zoom technology after getting their results in the pretest. And after that, the posttest was administered. Then, students were interviewed about their feedback on the use of Zoom in teaching Arabic pronunciation and their performance which has influenced in use of the features of Zoom technology as a learning platform.

This chapter includes answers to research questions: a) What is the students' feedback on the use of Zoom in teaching Arabic pronunciation? b) Is there a significant posttest gain in the Arabic pronunciation skills of students after being exposed to a zoom-based platform? c) Is there a significant difference in the Arabic pronunciation skills between the control and experimental groups? d) What are the features of using Zoom technology as a learning platform that influenced the performance of Arabic language students?

SUMMARY

In today's world, everything is changing rapidly. Arabic teaching and learning methods are changing as well. In the face of the Pandemic, many educational organizations have moved to online education like the Dar Ashifa'a Qur'an School. At this time, the use of information and communication technologies in teaching Arabic is one of the priorities of education, based on

which it possible to form the pronunciation skills of students continuously. The study revealed that Zoom technology has a highly positive effect on students' Arabic pronunciation skills.

The respondents of this study consisted of 50 Beginner students who are adults and learning Arabic as a foreign language. The students were divided into two groups such as the Control group with 25 students and the Experimental Group with 25 students. The experimental group had treatments or interventions. The results of the interventions revealed that they are significant proving that the pretest and post-test results had considerable differences between them. Table 5 shows that the treatment applied was effective in the Experimental Group. The positive results

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revealed that the Zoom technology is effective in developing pronunciation skills rather than the Non-Zoom technology.

The study gathered the student's results from pretest and posttest in both groups, the paired t-test was used in the Control group to assess whether there was a significant difference in pronunciation test scores before and after using the Non-Zoom Technology providing a statistical evaluation of the platform's effectiveness. The data in the experimental group is not normally distributed, therefore the Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to determine if there is a statistically significant change in the pronunciation test scores before and after their use of Zoom Technology. Thus, this test assesses the platform's effectiveness in improving pronunciation skills. The findings reveal that both the Control group and experimental group displayed significant score improvements

from the pretest to the posttest. The posttest gain score between the posttest and pretest was greater for the experimental group compared to the control group. This indicates that, on average, Beginner students in the experimental group who used the Zoom technology in the Arabic language classroom showed a greater improvement in pronunciation skills compared to those in the control group who used the Non-Zoom technology as a learning platform.

CONCLUSIONS

Learning to pronounce letters and words correctly is a process that begins with studying the language's sound system, various types of vocabulary, and sentence structures. In practice reading the Arabic language is not easy. Several things need to be considered in reading Arabic texts, especially in terms of pronunciation. Therefore, each letter must be spoken according to its articulation for the sake of fluency and accuracy in Arabic reading. Errors in pronunciation can cause differences in meaning or meaning errors in the text being read. For this reason, the correctness of reciting Arabic readings, especially the pronunciation of Arabic letters, is very important.

In this study, developing Arabic Pronunciation skills is confirmed by using Zoom technology to enhance students' performance in the Arabic language classroom. Zoom technology can also apply to the learning of different foreign languages. It shows that technology has a great effect on the Arabic language or any kind of language. Hence, technology has a significant role in the teaching and learning process. The use of

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communication network like Zoom technology in

learning foreign languages is the norm today. In this regard, the use and improvement of methods of the educational process and educational technology are of particular importance.

The quantitative result of the study revealed that the null hypothesis proved that there is a significant difference between the control and experimental groups and shows the significant difference between the groups through the pos-test gain scores found in Tables 4, 5 and 6. The intervention shows that both Non-Zoom technology and Zoom technology can be used to enhance pronunciation skills. However, the result shows that through Zoom technology, the students develop higher pronunciation skills rather than using Non-Zoom technology.

Whether Arabic is being acquired as a second language or a foreign language, both teachers and students should pay closer attention to the pronunciation teaching and learning process. Many people around the world have a strong desire to learn and speak Arabic with accurate pronunciation. Zoom technology as an online learning platform requires a special interactive approach. All participants in the class are expected to interact. The teacher should feel the audience and also try to get students' feedback.

In the qualitative result of the study, students' feedback was asked about their learning experience between Non-Zoom technology and utilizing Zoom-based platform. The beginner students' learning process of developing Arabic pronunciation is highly effective through Zoom technology. The students encountered some challenges in Zoom like the unstable internet connection and

meeting the specific device for Zoom but overall, there was an improvement in the learning process of the students, as they compared their experience before and after the intervention of Zoom technology.

Moreover, the features of Zoom technology play a vital role in the student pronunciation skills and it highly influences their performance in Arabic language pronunciation like Video-conferencing, Breakout rooms, Screen Sharing, and so forth.

In conclusion, many people of various professions, ages, and hobbies have engaged in both direct and indirect contact (using Zoom, for example) as a result of communication and technology advancements in society. Accordingly, the need to use a foreign language has also increased. Thus, the use and improvement of methods of the educational process and educational technology are of particular

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importance. By providing support, resources, and professional development opportunities, educators can find ways to create inclusive and effective Arabic instruction in pronunciation that caters to the needs of diverse learners.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The current study determined the effect of Zoom Technology in the Arabic language classroom on students' pronunciation skills. Therefore, it can be an alternative to traditional learning of Arabic pronunciation. However, several things affect how effective the Zoom technology is, including the professors' and students' digital literacy, establishing a significant interaction among all participants in distant courses, the lack of technical challenges, and the appropriate

of an effective teaching strategy. Based on the results of the research, some suggestions and strategies are given below which may help students and teachers in reducing difficulties in Arabic pronunciation using Zoom technology:

1. Increase instructors' awareness of students' pronunciation issues in the Arabic language. And how to create exercises to address them. In online platforms like Zoom, educators can sign up for specialized pronunciation training workshops and seminars. Especially in the Philippines, it is badly needed for qualified Arabic teachers in pronunciation.
2. Increase digital awareness among Arabic instructors on what tools, functions, and features of technology can be administered in an online pronunciation class.
3. Establishing a strong foundation in the Arabic Language: Students should be taught phonetics and phonology of the Arabic Language in their earlier stage of learning.
4. In an online platform, students should be provided with more pronunciation practices to improve their pronunciation performances.
5. Encourage collaborations with families and communities by involving them in helping students build their pronunciation abilities. Provide realistic and culturally appropriate learning opportunities that connect the Arabic language and real-world contexts by working with community groups and cultural institutions.

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6. By implementing these recommendations, institutions can create a supportive and effective language environment that enhances the pronunciation skills of students. Emphasizing the integration of language and mathematics instruction, providing differentiated support, and fostering partnerships with families and communities can lead to improved pronunciation outcomes and a deeper understanding of Arabic pronunciation.

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